

Original article

THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF PUBLIC SERVICES: E-GOVERNMENT IN THE EUROPEAN UNION

Petruț Cătălin LUNGU¹, Mircea Radu GEORGESCU², Teodora IRAVA³

¹Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, 0009-0005-5965-2657

²Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, 0000-0002-7022-3715

³Alexandru Ioan Cuza University of Iași, 0009-0004-5202-2399

Received: 15 January 2025

Revised: 23 March 2025

Accepted: 30 April 2025

Published: 2 May 2025

Citation:

LUNGU Petruț Cătălin, GEORGESCU Mircea Radu, IRAVA Teodora, 2025, "The Digital Transformation of Public Services: E-Government in the European Union", *Revista Economică*, 77(1), 7-12, May. DOI: 10.56043/reveco-2025-0001

Abstract: *The use of digital technologies to provide public services and facilitate citizen-government interactions has become a key priority for EU member states. Among the significant benefits of e-government are improved access to information, more effective communication, promoting communities and the rule of law, focusing on the needs of citizens, providing higher quality services, expanding working hours and reducing pressure on staff. Under these assumptions, the present study analyses the European situation in e-government adoption, highlighting both successes and challenges faced by different EU countries. Subsequently, we will highlight the impact of EU-wide policies and directives aimed at promoting digital transformation in public administration, as well as country-specific approaches and best practices. The research draws on case studies from various member states to illustrate the diversity of e-government solutions and their effectiveness in enhancing public service delivery, increasing transparency, and fostering citizen engagement. Lastly, the study also investigates the challenges that persist in the widespread adoption of e-government solutions, including issues related to data privacy and security, the digital divide, interoperability of systems, and the need for continuous technological upgrades.*

Keywords: Digital Transformation, Public Administration, E-Government, European Union

JEL classification: H11, H83

Copyright: © 2025 by the authors. Submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

1. Introduction

The European Union's public administration and governance landscape has seen a substantial transformation due to the swift development of digital technology. For EU member states, e-government—the use of digital tools and platforms to provide government services and promote citizen-government interactions—has become a strategic priority. The use of digital technologies for enhancing accountability, transparency, and citizen participation in governance processes has been referred to as e-governance (Troitiño, D.R., Mazur, V., Kerikmäe, T., 2024). When integrated, these concepts – e-governance and e-government – provide an extensive approach for updating public administration in the digital era.

Numerous potential advantages accompany this move to e-government, such as better information access, more effective communication, increased openness, and more specialized public services. E-governance, on the other hand, makes sure that these developments are in line with democratic ideals, promoting inclusivity and trust in interactions between the public and the government.

The present paper provides an investigation of the adoption and implementation of e-government throughout the European Union as of today. The current study explores the nowadays situation of e-government within the European Union, taking into consideration their efforts to digitally transform the public sector. To provide a comprehensive picture of the e-government environment, the analysis makes use of official information from the United Nations and the European Commission, emphasizing both the top-performing and underperforming nations.

¹ petrut3008@gmail.com *- corresponding author

² mirceag@uaic.ro

³ teodora.irava@gmail.com

Overall, this comprehensive analysis of e-government in the European Union offers a robust foundation for understanding the current state of digital transformation in public administration, paving the way for further advancements and the realization of the full potential of e-government across the continent.

2. Literature review

The concept of e-government aligns with the broader approach to governance, defined as the set of mechanisms, processes, and institutions through which governmental and non-governmental actors interact to make and implement public decisions (Bevir, 2012). This conceptualization emphasizes the role of government as well as other social actors in the formulation and implementation of public policies. In this context, democratic governance refers to a governmental decision-making process that is open or public, accountable, transparent, and equitable in respecting individual privacy (Palanisamy, 2004). E-governance is an essential component of this democratic governance model, reflecting the migration of governmental activities and services to the digital environment (Coursey, D., Norris, D.F., 2008). In other words, e-governance serves as a critical tool in promoting open and transparent decision-making processes among public authorities (Bertot, J.C., Jaeger, P.T., Grimes, J.M., 2016).

The primary goal of implementing e-government concepts is to satisfy citizens as clients by providing online public services, while also facilitating access to government information and fostering interactive engagement between the government and the public (Norris, 2013). This approach integrates information technology, human resources, and governmental structures, representing a fundamental transformation in the way public authorities fulfill their obligations toward citizens (Parycek, P., Höchtl, J., Ginner, M., 2014). Significant benefits of e-government include improved access to information, more efficient communication, the promotion of community engagement and the rule of law, a focus on citizens' needs, the provision of higher-quality services, extended operational hours, and reduced pressure on personnel. However, challenges related to infrastructure, security, digital literacy, and public acceptance must be appropriately addressed to ensure a smooth transition toward a technology-driven, citizen-centered government (Shao, D., Ishengoma, F.R., Alexopoulos, C., Saxena, S., Nikiforova, A., Matheus, R., 2023).

Overall, e-government represents a fundamental transformation in the way governments interact with citizens, provide information, and deliver services. It serves as a critical tool for ensuring transparency, efficiency, and accountability in public administration in the digital era. Consequently, implementing e-government is a strategic priority for modernizing public administration and increasing citizen satisfaction in today's digital age. In essence, e-government goes beyond simply equipping institutions with computers or creating websites for information access. It entails a profound transformation of the relationship between government and the public. This involves reshaping how government services are delivered by leveraging technology. Government agencies must continually focus on:

1. Identifying the government functions.
2. Responsibly transforming existing business models by integrating new and emerging technologies.
3. Ensuring that these new business models reflect the collective concerns and priorities of the public.

This approach enables public institutions to optimize operations, remain relevant in the digital era, and effectively respond to the needs of citizens (Nookhao, S., Kiattisin, S., 2023).

In the context of the accelerated growth of internet usage, both developing and developed countries have significantly adopted digital technologies to provide efficient and effective public services to their citizens. Beyond improving service delivery, the internet has substantially contributed to enhancing transparency in governance and has brought numerous benefits to the e-governance community (Kalampokis, E., Karacapilidis, N., Tsakalidis, D., Tarabanis, K., 2023). For example, in nowadays, the deployment of chatbots has effectively reduced service delivery costs, improved personnel workloads, and shortened citizens' waiting times for service help, notwithstanding the possibility of unanticipated beneficial results for public administrations (Cortés-Cediel, M.E., Segura-Tinoco, A., Cantador, I., Bolívar, M.P.R., 2023).

3. Methodology

From a methodological point of view, the present paper aims to analyse the European situation in e-government adoption, highlighting both successes and challenges faced by different EU countries. For achieving the proposed goal, a review of the academic literature on e-government and e-governance was undertaken. Complementary, an analysis of the available data was performed, using official datasets from the European Commission (e.g., eGovernment Benchmark reports) and the United Nations (e.g., E-Government Development Index, EGDI). To fulfil the landscape of the adoption of e-government within the European Union's countries, different case studies were taken into consideration and comparative analysis was adopted for comparing the performance of European countries.

4. Results and discussions

The evolution of e-administration marks a critical technological and organizational shift, integrating digital tools and strategies to redesign government workflows, improving operational efficiency, and provide more responsive and personalized public services (Troitiño, D.R., Mazur, V., Kerikmäe, T. , 2024). The adoption of e-Government across European Union member states has accelerated post-COVID-19, driven by the need to expand digital services. This shift enhances interactions between governments and citizens, streamlining public administration processes (Campmas, A., Jacob, N., Simonelli, F., 2022). For providing a clear landscape on the e-government within the European Union, we will proceed to a brief analyze of the available data. In this context, an important indicator is represented by the *e-Government maturity score* provided by the European Commission. The results are systematically illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Overall eGovernment maturity score

Source: European Commission, 2023, eGovernment Benchmark 2023 Insight Report

According to the available data, Malta and Estonia lead the way with the highest overall eGovernment maturity scores of 96 and 92 respectively. This indicates they have the most advanced and effective digital government services and infrastructure among European countries. Taking into consideration the sub-dimensions of the indicator, it can be stated that Malta leads in the *Transparency* key dimension, with Iceland and Luxembourg following closely behind. Similarly, Lithuania, Iceland, and Malta are the top-performing countries in the *Key Enablers* dimension, showcasing strong implementation of critical digital tools like eID, digital signatures, and secure digital mailboxes. Particularly, Malta, and Finland lead in *User-centric services*, each achieving a remarkable score of 99. Luxembourg, Estonia, and Malta stand out for offering online services to non-nationals that are almost on par with those provided to their own citizens (*Cross-Border Services*).

Another instrument for measuring the level of e-government is *E-government Development Index* (EGDI), provided by the United Nations. The information related to the European Union of the last report, published in 2024, is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: E-government Development Index

Source: United Nations, 2024, E-government Development Index

The data reveals that the Nordic countries, especially Denmark, Estonia, and Finland, are leading the way with the highest EGDI scores, all exceeding 0.95. This indicates they have built robust digital government infrastructures and services that are highly accessible and effective for their citizens. Denmark leads the rankings with a score of 0.9847, closely followed by Estonia (0.9727) and Finland (0.9575). These nations demonstrate exceptional use of technology to deliver efficient and high-quality public services, supported by robust digital infrastructure, innovative policy frameworks, and active citizen engagement.

In contrast, countries like Romania, Slovakia, Hungary, and Bulgaria lag with EGDI scores below 0.82, suggesting more work is needed to integrate digital technologies and improve the online delivery of public services. These are struggling with systemic issues such as limited infrastructure, low digital literacy, or slow policy adaptation. Romania's significantly lower score suggests challenges in bridging the digital divide and modernizing public administration.

At the European and international levels, Estonia is often highlighted as a success story in e-government implementation (Goede, 2019). Academic literature emphasizes that Estonia's transition to e-government began in the 1990s, following its independence. One key factor attributed to its rapid digital transformation is the lack of pre-existing infrastructure, which allowed Estonia to adopt advanced digital solutions directly (Kalvet, T., Aaviksoo, A., 2018).

Assuming the analyzed data, Estonia is a notable performer in the European e-government landscape, coming in second on the E-Government Development Index (EGDI) and the eGovernment Maturity Score. This Baltic country has gained notoriety for its inventive efforts at digital transformation and has become a global leader in the delivery of effective and creative public services. Estonia's long-standing focus to digital infrastructure and citizen-centric policy is the cornerstone of its e-government success (Lnenicka, M., Luterek, M., Majo, L.T., 2024). The nation has made significant investments to create a strong digital backbone, which includes eID adoption on a large scale, secure digital signatures, and efficient digital data interchange systems (Androniceanu, A., Georgescu, I., 2021) (Jalakas, 2018).

Additionally, it can be stated that Estonia has advanced significantly due to its inclusive and cooperative approach to e-governance. To get input and keep improving service delivery, the government has actively engaged with enterprises, citizens, and other stakeholders (Kitsing, 2011). Estonia has been able to quickly forward its digital agenda and establish itself as a model for other European countries hoping to follow its e-government success because to this participatory methodology, a forward-thinking regulatory framework, and an adept at technology population.

Summarizing the previous aspects, it can be stated that the member states of the European Union have achieved major progress in e-Government, with Estonia, Malta, and Denmark setting the standard for digital maturity and innovation. These countries are examples of how inclusive policymaking and strong digital infrastructure may improve the provision of public services. Disparities still exist, though, as some governments have structural obstacles that restrict them from implementing e-Government.

5. Conclusions

To conclude, the analysis of e-government within the European Union presents a nuanced and evolving landscape, marked by both successes and persistent challenges. The data gathered from the European Commission's eGovernment Maturity Score, and the United Nations' E-Government Development Index (EGDI) offers a comprehensive view of the digital transformation progress across EU member states.

The findings indicate that countries such as Malta, Estonia, and the Nordic nations of Finland, Denmark, and Sweden have emerged as leaders in e-government implementation, demonstrating a strong commitment to digital infrastructure, citizen-centric service delivery, and innovative policy frameworks. These frontrunners have not only achieved high overall scores but have also excelled in specific dimensions, such as transparency, key enablers, and user-centricity.

In contrast, several member states, including Romania, Slovakia, Hungary, and Bulgaria, continue to lag, confronting systemic issues related to limited digital infrastructure, low digital literacy, and slow policy adaptation. This uneven progress highlights the need for continued investment, capacity-building, and knowledge-sharing across the EU to ensure more equitable digital transformation of public administration.

E-governance, as a complementary framework, plays a critical role in ensuring that digital transformation aligns with democratic principles, fostering transparency, accountability, and citizen participation. While e-government focuses on service delivery, e-governance ensures that these services are delivered in a manner that builds trust and inclusiveness.

Considering the significant differences among EU member states, future research will focus on providing frameworks for understanding both the ethical and technical challenges of e-government adoption. Even though infrastructure investment and coordinated governance have helped the Nordic and Baltic regions develop digital service ecosystems, issues like cross-border authentication, GDPR compliance, legacy system interoperability, and the incorporation of artificial intelligence into administrative procedures still need to be thoroughly investigated. Although case studies of Portugal's Simplex program, Denmark's Digital Post, and Estonia's X-Road provide insightful information, future research is required to adopt and adapt these models in other countries, to successfully achieve a balance between innovation and privacy, security, and interoperability in the rapidly changing digital transformation landscape.

By understanding the nuances of e-government adoption and the factors driving both success and struggle, policymakers and public administrators can develop more targeted and effective strategies to accelerate the digitalization of government services and solidify the EU's position as a global leader in e-government.

References

1. Androniceanu, A., Georgescu, I., 2021. E-Government in European countries, a comparative approach using the Principal Components Analysis. *NISPACEE Journal of Public Administration and Policy*, 14(2), pp. 65-86.
2. Bertot, J.C., Jaeger, P.T., Grimes, J.M., 2016. Using ICTs to create a culture of transparency: E-government and social media as openness and anti-corruption tools for societies. *Government information quarterly*, 27(3), pp. 264-271.
3. Bevir, M., 2012. *Governance: A very short introduction*. Oxford: OUP.
4. Campmas, A., Iacob, N., Simonelli, F., 2022. How can interoperability stimulate the use of digital public services? An analysis of national interoperability frameworks and e-Government in the European Union. *Data & Policy*, 4(19).
5. Cortés-Cediel, M.E., Segura-Tinoco, A., Cantador, I., Bolívar, M.P.R., 2023. Trends and challenges of e-government chatbots: Advances in exploring open government data and citizen participation content. *Government Information Quarterly*, 40(4), p. 10187.
6. Coursey, D., Norris, D.F., 2008. Models of e-government: Are they correct? An empirical assessment. *Public administration review*, 68(3), pp. 523-536.
7. European Commission, 2023. *eGovernment Benchmark 2023 Insight Report - Connecting Digital Governments*, <https://digital-decade-desi.digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/>: European Commission.
8. Goede, M., 2019. E-Estonia: The e-government cases of Estonia, Singapore, and Curaçao. *Policy & Governance Review*, 7(2), pp. 140-153.
9. Jalakas, P., 2018. Blockchain from public administration perspective: Case of Estonia. *Tallinn University of Technology*.
10. Kalampokis, E., Karacapilidis, N., Tsakalidis, D., Tarabanis, K., 2023. Understanding the use of Emerging technologies in the public sector: A review of Horizon 2020 projects. *Digital Government: Research and Practice*, 4(1), pp. 1-28.

11. Kalvet, T., Aaviksoo, A., 2018. The Development of eServices in an Enlarged EU: eGovernment and eHealth in Estonia.. *Joint Research Centre - Institute for Prospective Technological Studies*, pp. 1-121.
12. Kitsing, M., 2011. Success without strategy: E-government development in Estonia. *Policy & Internet*, 1(1-21), p. 3.
13. Lnenicka, M., Luterek, M., Majo, L.T., 2024. Analysis of e-government and digital society indicators over the years: a comparative study of the EU member states. *Digital Policy, Regulation and Governance*, 26(5), pp. 560-582.
14. Nookhao, S., Kiattisin, S., 2023. Achieving a successful e-government: Determinants of behavioral intention from Thai citizens' perspective. *Heliyon*, 9(8).
15. Norris, D. R. C., 2013. Local e-government in the United States: Transformation or incremental change?. *Public Administration Review*, 73(1), pp. 165-175.
16. Palanisamy, R., 2004. Issues and challenges in e-governance planning. *Electronic Government, an International Journal*, 1(3), pp. 253-272.
17. Parycek, P., Höchtl, J., Ginner, M., 2014. Open government data implementation evaluation. *Journal of theoretical and applied electronic commerce research*, 9(2), pp. 80-99.
18. Shao, D., Ishengoma, F.R., Alexopoulos, C., Saxena, S., Nikiforova, A., Matheus, R., 2023. Integration of IoT into e-government. *Foresight*, 25(5), pp. 734-750.
19. Troitiño, D.R., Mazur, V., Kerikmäe, T., 2024. E-governance and integration in the European Union. *Internet of Things*, 27(101321).
20. United Nations, 2024. *E-government Development Index*, New York: <https://publicadministration.un.org/egovkb/en-us/Reports/UN-E-Government-Survey-2024>.